

Framing Data Literacy.

The Competence Centre for Data Literacy QUADRIGA

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Abstract

The Berlin-Brandenburg Competence Centre for Data Literacy QUADRIGA [1] develops Open Educational Resources (OERs) for researchers in the fields of Digital Humanities and Public Administration based on case studies. These case studies focus on the data types text, table and moving image. Questions from the application domains of Digital Humanities and Public Administration are addressed with the support of Computer Science and Information Science.

Research case studies are enhanced didactically (e.g. prepared for learners with added assessment options) and prepared as OERs [2], which are then tested and integrated with all four communities. Through these OERs, researchers can go through different phases of research data management and learn how to apply good research data management.

QUADRIGA's objective is to impart discipline-specific data skills to researchers at all career levels. These data skills are mapped using a QUADRIGA-specific data literacy framework [3], which is based on the framework for "Data Literacy Education" [4], the "Future Skills Framework" of the Hochschulforum Digitalisierung [5], the EOSC-initiated "FAIR4S Framework" [6], and the "Pilot Competency Matrix for Data Management Skills" [7] and customized for the QUADRIGA use scenarios and domains. The framework comprises different dimensions of data literacy, such as a data flow, which includes planning, collection/reuse, enrichment/adjustment, analysis and other steps. Dimensions for data skills/knowledge and examples are also addressed [8]. The OERs are published in the QUADRIGA Space, and the OERs can be searched in the QUADRIGA Navigator by metadata and based on the data literacy framework.

After 1,5 years, nearly six comprehensive OERs are online. The QUADRIGA Navigator will go live during the annual conference in June 2025. A whole series of data competence events took place and more are already being planned. The paper shows previous results and presents the resources created in more detail.

Keywords: Data Literacy, Open Educational Resources, OER

Resources

- Reproduzierbarkeit von Datenanalysen. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14999803> "First Open Educational Resource of data type table"
- Affektrhetorik in Online-Videos zur Klimakrise. Datengestützte Analysen audiovisueller Muster. quadriga-dk.github.io/Bewegtes-Bild-Fallstudie-1/ "First Open Educational Resource of data type moving image"
- Erfragen von Metadaten: Ein Fallbeispiel aus dem Europäischen und Deutschen Metadatenportal. <https://quadriga-dk.github.io/Tabelle-Fallstudie-2> "Second Open Educational Resource of data type table"
- Quantitative Analyse der Medienwellen der Spanischen Grippe (1918/19). Eine Fallstudie. <https://dh-network.github.io/quadriga/markdown/intro.html> "First Open Educational Resource of data type text"
- Quantitative diachrone Analyse der kommunikativen Barrierefreiheit des Berliner Senats (2011–2024). Eine Fallstudie. <https://quadriga-dk.github.io/Text-Fallstudie-2> "Second Open Educational Resource of data type text"
- QUADRIGA-Datenkompetenzframework. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15058057> "Model of the QUADRIGA Data Competence Framework."
- Das QUADRIGA-Datenkompetenzframework als Basis für die Entwicklung von Lehr- und Lernressourcen. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14925620> "Paper describes aim and development of the QUADRIGA Data Competence Framework"
- Datenkompetenzerwerb mit OER: QUADRIGA — das Berlin-Brandenburgische Datenkompetenzzentrum für Digital Humanities, Verwaltungswissenschaften, Informatik und Informationswissenschaft. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14925618> "Paper describes first six Open Educational Resources and maps them to their data competences"
- Vorstellung des Berlin-Brandenburgischen Datenkompetenzzentrums QUADRIGA für Digital Humanities, Verwaltungswissenschaften, Informatik und Informationswissenschaft. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13889204> "Video shows presentation of Data Competence Center at its first annual conference"
- QUADRIGA Podiumsdiskussion über Datenkompetenz. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13951240> "Video shows podium discussion on data competences at first QUADRIGA annual conference"
- QUADRIGA OERs: erstellen und gestalten mit Jupyter Book. QUADRIGA Open Educational Resources: Template. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15004730> "Template of all QUADRIGA Open Educational Resources"

Author contributions

Melanie Seltmann: Conceptualization, Writing – original draft

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Bettina Buchholz: Project administration

Ulrike Lucke: Project administration

Evgenia Samoilova: Project administration

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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